

EXAMINATION ROUTE OF BREAST CANCER THROUGH MODERN SCREENING

Mamedov Umid Sunnatovich¹

Juraev Nodir Ablokulovich²

Khalikova Feruza Sharofovna³

¹⁻²⁻³State Medical Institute Bukhara, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7407702>

Relevance: Of the 10 million new cases of malignant tumors of various organs detected in the world, 10% are in the mammary gland. If we estimate only the female population, the proportion of breast cancer increases to 22%. In 2020 Breast cancer identified from 471 million women in developing countries, i.e., most often cervical cancer (379 million), the leader in the preceding years. The ideology of screening is based on the fact that routine clinical examination and selfexamination usually do not provide detection of curable forms of cancer. Therefore, it is necessary to use such instrumental diagnostic methods. drugs that would detect manifestations of significantly earlier forms of tumors that can be cured by existing surgical, chemohormonal, or radiation treatments. X-ray mammography was the most suitable method for this purpose. Screening involves the use of a method for detecting latent pathology in a large group of practically healthy individuals and therefore must meet the following requirements: High sensitivity of the applied method or test, which makes it possible to detect the majority of malignant tumors in the examined group with a minimum number of false negative conclusions.

The aim of study: To review breast cancer screening, especially in the community and to examine evidence about new screening modalities.

Materials and methods: The evaluation of screening modalities, especially in the community setting, is challenging for methodological, clinical, and ethical reasons. Randomized clinical trials are considered the gold standard for evaluating a new screening test. The long-term breast cancer mortality rate of women randomized to receive a new screening test is compared with that of women randomized to receive standard care. However, such trials are difficult to conduct. They require tens of thousands of women who need to be followed up for more than 15 years. Furthermore, because mammography screening has been shown to be effective in some trials, it would likely be even more difficult to demonstrate any additional efficacy of new tests. Finally, as treatment for breast cancer has improved over time, the impact of screening on breast cancer mortality may be increasingly difficult to establish.

Results: Concerns related to flaws of these randomized clinical trials have been raised. In-depth independent reviews of the criticisms of the trials have concluded that these flaws do not negate mammography's efficacy in reducing breast cancer mortality, especially in women aged 50 to 69 years. Trials comparing mammography with or without clinical breast examination to usual care (with little or no screening mammography) demonstrated remarkably consistent results for women older than 50 years. Meta-analyses that included all trials demonstrated statistically significant reductions of 20% to 35% in mortality from breast cancer for women aged 50 to 69 years.⁷ The majority of participants in clinical trials of mammography were white and information on BRCA mutation status was not known.

Conclusion: We have also emphasized the challenge of evaluating new screening modalities. Newer screening tests such as MRI and ultrasound have been studied in women at increased risk of breast cancer (eg, carriers of BRCA1 or BRCA2 mutations).

